

Iodometric Determination of some Inorganic Oxidants in Binary Mixture by Selective Decompositions of One of the Components

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The individual components of binary mixtures composed of MnO_4^- , BrO_3^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, and IO_3^- have been determined iodometrically employing apposite organic substrates to decompose selectively and quantitatively one of the oxidants. In the aqueous solution the MnO_4^- reacted with cinnamic acid to furnish an insoluble derivative which was separated by filtration from the other oxidant followed by estimation of each ingredient. When BrO_3^- was present with $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, the former was decomposed completely with KBr in the presence of dilute acid and acetanilide at room temperature. Iodometric estimation of IO_3^- in the presence of either BrO_3^- or $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ was carried out using potassium hydrogen phthalate or formalin to decompose BrO_3^- or $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$. The total amount of oxidant was determined iodometrically in every mixture to calculate the quantities of each component.

Various methods of estimation of MnO_4^- , BrO_3^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and IO_3^- when present singly have been reported¹⁻³ but very little information is available regarding their estimation in the binary mixtures. The MnO_4^- - $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ mixture had been estimated by oxalic acid or sodium oxalate in the presence of MnSO_4 catalyst⁴. The latter was necessary for the reduction of Mn^{VII} at room temperature. Another method using H_2O_2 and Na_2CO_3 for the determination of Cr^{VI} in the presence of Mn^{VII} is available⁵. It has been observed during our investigations that complete decomposition of H_2O_2 is not possible by heating as long as 2 h, thus leading to inaccurate determination of Cr^{VI} . Several instrumental methods for estimating MnO_4^- in the presence of other oxidants have been reported⁶. A redox titrimetric method for the simultaneous determination of Ce^{IV} , Mn^{VII} and Cr^{VI} has been reported⁷. Apart from these instrumental techniques only a few methods of estimation of BrO_3^- - IO_3^- mixture have been reported^{2,8}. In the present paper several simple and inexpensive

chemical methods of analysis requiring no instrumental technique have been reported.

Results and Discussion

The determinations of the individual components of mixtures of strong oxidants like Mn^{VII} , Cr^{VI} , Br^{V} and I^{V} by purely chemical method appeared to be interesting. The close proximity of the E_0 values of these oxidants [$\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}} \rightarrow \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ ($E_0 = 1.54$ V), $\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}} \rightarrow \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ ($E_0 = 1.36$ V), $\text{Br}^{\text{V}} \rightarrow \text{Br}^-$ ($E_0 = 1.44$ V), $\text{I}^{\text{V}} \rightarrow \text{I}^-$ ($E_0 = 1.08$ V)]¹⁻³ makes it difficult to estimate them individually in the mixtures. It was anticipated that simple organic compounds should selectively and quantitatively decompose one of the components of a binary mixtures of the oxidants under suitable conditions of the temperature and the acidity of the solution. Oxalic acid, formic acid, formaldehyde solution (35%), various alcohols and other classes of organic compounds were tried for the selective decomposition of MnO_4^- in the mixture. But all of them affected BrO_3^- , albeit slowly. It was envisaged that MnO_4^-

could react selectively with olefinic compounds, preferably the solid olefins. Out of several unsaturated compounds investigated only cinnamic acid was found to be most suitable for the removal of Mn^{VII} as it furnished a brown derivative which was insoluble in both water and ethanol. Initially a column (3 cm) of an intimate mixture of cinnamic acid and powdered glass (1 : 1; w/w) was prepared. The MnO_4^- - BrO_3^- mixture was quantitatively transferred on the column. The colourless solution filtering through the column was free from MnO_4^- and the BrO_3^- contained in filtrate could be accurately determined. But this method was quite time-consuming and irksome for the estimation of manganese derivative. Hence the modified procedure described under Methods A and B were adopted (Experimental). The BrO_3^- present in the filtrate was estimated iodometrically. The amount of MnO_4^- in the mixture was calculated by subtracting this amount (BrO_3^-) from the amount of total oxidants (Table 1). The mixture of MnO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ was successfully estimated (Table 1), and the uv-vis spectrum for the filtrate showed the absorption maxima of Cr^{VI} only at 348 nm⁹. Similarly MnO_4^- - IO_3^- was estimated.

The amounts of MnO_4^- obtained by Method B were 0.75 to 1.2% lower than those determined by iodometric and Mohr's solution methods. In the direct estimation of MnO_4^- from the manganese derivative by Method B, the following calculation has been adopted. If same volumes of the Mohr's salt solution required (a) and (b) ml of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ of strength $S(N)$ before and after the experiment and the volume of KMnO_4 taken be V (ml), then the amount of KMnO_4 (P) is given by

$$(P) = \frac{[(a) - (b)] \times S}{V} \times 31.606 \text{ g l}^{-1}$$

(equivalent weight of $\text{KMnO}_4 = 31.606$)

It has been observed, however, that this method is not suitable for $\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}-\text{V}^{\text{V}}$, $\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}-\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}$, $\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}-\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ systems where water-insoluble brown precipitate does not appear. In $\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}-\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}$ system both the oxidants are affected by cinnamic acid.

It was observed that formalin in H_2SO_4 (1M) could be successfully employed for determining the constituents of IO_3^- - $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and IO_3^- - BrO_3^- mixtures. The present investigation shows that the quantitative decomposition of BrO_3^- in BrO_3^- - IO_3^- mixture could be achieved more easily by adopting any one of the methods D and E (Experimental). The Method C was suitable for BrO_3^- - $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ system but unsuitable for BrO_3^- - IO_3^- mixture (Experimental).

The Method D was successful only with dilute solution of BrO_3^- . With MnO_4^- - IO_3^- mixture this method could be applied when the concentration of MnO_4^- was low. One similar method of analysis of multicomponent system was reported by Szekeres¹⁰. In Method E, potassium hydrogen phthalate (1-2 g) at 30-35° was used² to suppress the reaction rate between BrO_3^- and I^- . The use of large excess of the reagent caused drifting of the end-point¹¹. By similar method, potassium hydrogen phthalate has been used for $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ - IO_3^- mixture (Table 4). The IO_3^- - I^- reaction was complete within 2 min, and the liberated I_2 was estimated. The reaction mixture was immediately treated with a small amount of NaHCO_3 followed by H_2SO_4 (10 ml; 1M) and the I_2 liberated from $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and I^- reaction was estimated (Table 4). Thus the components of the $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ - IO_3^- mixture could be determined in a single-pot reaction.

Experimental

Cinnamic and oxalic acids, formaldehyde (35%; Merck), acetanilide, potassium hydrogen phthalate, syrupy phosphoric acid, KBr, Mohr's salt, NaBiO_3 (all of very pure grade), KMnO_4 , KBrO_3 , $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, KIO_3 , KI (all of G.R., Merck), $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (Merck), HCl , H_2SO_4 (A.R.) were used. Double-distilled water (prepared by refluxing over KMnO_4) was used throughout. Uv spectra were taken in Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer.

Procedure : Primary standard solutions of KBrO_3 (0.0167 M), KIO_3 (0.0157 M), $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (0.0161 M) and oxalic acid (0.0504 M) were prepared.

Secondary standard solutions of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ and KMnO_4 were prepared and estimated using standard $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and oxalic acid solutions respectively¹. The strength of KMnO_4 solution was also determined by standard Mohr's salt solution and iodometric methods.

Effect of cinnamic acid on KMnO_4 in aqueous solution : A standard jointed (B-24) sintered glass funnel (50 ml; porosity 3), whose stem being connected through a side-tube to a water aspirator during filtration, was used. Cinnamic acid (~1 g) was shaken with water (10 ml), then filtered through this funnel thereby depositing a thin layer of cinnamic acid on the filter bed. In a glass-stoppered Erlenmeyer flask (100 ml) was taken KMnO_4 (10 ml ; 0.0189 M). Cinnamic acid (0.3 g) was added to it with vigorous shaking for 10 min at 30–35° (room temperature). The supernatant liquid rapidly became colourless and a dark brown precipitate settled down. The reaction mixture was filtered through the above mentioned sintered glass funnel under water suction to a standard jointed (B-24) Erlenmeyer flask used as receiver. The filtrate was acidified with H_2SO_4 (1M) and tested for the presence of MnO_4^- with starch-iodide solution which, however, indicated the absence of MnO_4^- in the filtrate. It also did not show purple colouration on treatment with HNO_3 and NaBiO_3 indicating that the brown manganese derivative was insoluble in water. The uv-vis spectrum of the filtrate also indicated the absence of absorption at 525–550 nm⁹ confirming complete removal of MnO_4^- by cinnamic acid (Method A).

The brown precipitate obtained as residue was thoroughly washed with ethanol followed by water, then dissolved by dropwise addition of fuming HNO_3 (3 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (3 ml), and collecting the solution quantitatively in the receiver. A glass funnel was placed on the neck of this flask which was then heated over a controlled flame in a fume chamber in such a way that the brown fumes were completely removed within 40 min when oily drops were found to condense from the dense white fumes on the inside wall of the flask. After 1 h the mixture was cooled and diluted with water

(70 ml) so as to maintain the normality of the solution between 2.5 and 3.0. To this solution, NaBiO_3 (1.5 g) was added portionwise with thorough shaking for at least 10 min, then the reaction mixture was filtered through the sintered glass funnel directly into the receiver containing known excess of standard Mohr's salt solution and syrupy phosphoric acid (5 ml). The residue was washed with 3% H_2SO_4 (8 × 5 ml) until free from Mn^{VII} . The washings were collected in the same Mohr's salt solution, the excess of which was titrated with standard dichromate solution in the usual way to determine the amount of Mn^{VII} (Method B).

The effect of cinnamic acid was studied separately on the aqueous solutions of BrO_3^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and IO_3^- (Method A). But all of these oxidants were found to remain unaffected by cinnamic acid under the experimental conditions.

Total oxidants : The total amounts of iodine liberated from the binary mixtures of the oxidants were determined by usual iodometric method for calculation of the total oxidant in the mixtures.

Estimation of KBrO_3 and KMnO_4 when present in a mixture : A mixture of KMnO_4 (10 ml; 2.3348 g l^{-1}) and KBrO_3 (10 ml ; 2.3279 g l^{-1}) was shaken for 10 min with cinnamic acid (0.3 g) when the supernatant liquid became colourless (about 5 min) with the brown precipitate settling down. The reaction mixture was then filtered through the bed of cinnamic acid on the sintered glass funnel as described before. The filtrate was free from Mn^{VII} . The residue was washed with water (5 ml for each washing) until two consecutive washings were free from BrO_3^- (tested with acidified starch-iodide solution). This required approximately 40 ml of water. The combined filtrate was treated with H_2SO_4 (10 ml; 1 M) followed by KI (1.5 g) and then left for 5 min in dark. The liberated I_2 was titrated in the usual way with $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution of known strength. Different sets of KMnO_4 – KBrO_3 mixtures were treated in this way (Method A), to determine the amounts of BrO_3^- in each case. The amount of Mn^{VII} in the residue was

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF BrO_3^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ AND IO_3^- IN DIFFERENT BINARY MIXTURES WITH MnO_4^- (BY METHOD A)

Amount of KMnO_4 used in all mixtures were determined by (i) iodometry = 2.3348 g/l, (ii) Method B = 2.3183 g/l¹

Sl no of mixture of oxidant	Amount of KBrO_3 (g l^{-1})		Amount of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (g l^{-1})		Amount of KIO_3 (g l^{-1})	
	Actual	Found* / (Standard deviation)	Actual	Found* / (Standard deviation)	Actual	Found* / (Standard deviation)
1	2.3279	2.3116 ($\pm 1.3 \times 10^{-3}$)	2.3799	2.3673 ($\pm 1.28 \times 10^{-3}$)	6.5926	6.6478 ($\pm 8.21 \times 10^{-3}$)
2	0.5515	0.5527 ($\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$)	1.2787	1.2704 ($\pm 5.2 \times 10^{-3}$)	3.6674	3.6619 ($\pm 5.3 \times 10^{-3}$)
3	0.3486	0.3470 ($\pm 0.92 \times 10^{-3}$)	0.3408	0.3399 ($\pm 1.7 \times 10^{-3}$)	3.3366	3.3333 ($\pm 6.07 \times 10^{-3}$)
4	0.2837	0.2839 ($\pm 0.1 \times 10^{-2}$)	0.2647	0.2654 ($\pm 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$)	1.5370	1.5274 ($\pm 8.4 \times 10^{-4}$)
5	0.1528	0.1535 ($\pm 0.5 \times 10^{-2}$)	0.1932	0.1945 ($\pm 7.3 \times 10^{-4}$)	0.0498	0.0494 ($\pm 1.8 \times 10^{-4}$)
6	0.0658	0.0644 ($\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$)	0.1065	0.1054 ($\pm 9.5 \times 10^{-4}$)	0.0143	0.0143 (0)

* Average of 6 determinations

determined either by Method B or calculated from the difference of the iodometric titre values of the mixture before and after the application of Method A. Results are given in Table 1. Method A was extremely suitable for the aqueous mixtures of MnO_4^- with $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ or IO_3^- and the oxidants could be determined very accurately. The amounts of MnO_4^- in these cases were determined either by Method B or from the difference of titre values (Table 1).

Estimation of BrO_3^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ in a mixture :

In order to determine the constituents of BrO_3^- - $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ mixture various organic substances were tried to find out a suitable scavenger for Br_2 which caused interference in iodometric titrations. Acetanilide was found to be most effective for this purpose for arresting Br_2 in the reaction mixture. Thus the mixture of BrO_3^- (10 ml; 0.01 M) and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (10 ml; 0.01 M) was treated with glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and acetanilide (1.0 g). This solution was shaken for 5 min with HCl (10 ml; 6M) and KBr (0.5 g). Thereby BrO_3^- was decomposed completely and the residual $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ was determined by the usual iodometry (Method C, Table 2).

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ IN DIFFERENT $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ - BrO_3^- MIXTURES (METHOD C)

Amount of KBrO_3 taken in all the mixtures = 2.4924 g dl⁻¹
(Found* = 2.4832 g dl⁻¹)

Sl no of mixture of oxidants	Amount of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (g l^{-1})		Standard deviation
	Actual	Found*	
1	4.7892	4.8760	$\pm 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$
2	1.4340	1.4156	$\pm 9.5 \times 10^{-4}$
3	0.6354	0.6352	$\pm 1.1 \times 10^{-2}$

* Average of 6 determinations

Estimation of BrO_3^- and IO_3^- in a mixture :

This was effected by heating the mixture of BrO_3^- (10 ml; 0.01 M) and IO_3^- (10 ml; 0.01 M) and H_2SO_4 (10 ml; 1 M) on a steam-bath for 5 min. Formalin (35% ; 5 drops) was then added with shaking. After 2 min formalin (2 drops) was again added and the heating was continued for 2-3 min. The colourless reaction mixture was immediately cooled, diluted with water (10 ml) and IO_3^- was determined (Method D ; Table 3).

Estimation of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and IO_3^- in a mixture :

A mixture of IO_3^- (10 ml; 0.01 M) and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (10 ml; 0.01 M) was shaken with potassium hydrogen

phthalate (3 g) in water² (100 ml), then treated with KI (1.5 g) to estimate IO_3^- in the usual way. The reaction mixture was then treated with H_2SO_4 (20 ml; 1 M) and the liberated I_2 was estimated to determine $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (Method E ; Table 4).

 TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF IO_3^- FROM DIFFERENT BrO_3^- —

IO_3^- MIXTURES (METHOD D)
 Amount of KBrO_3 taken = 2.4924 g dl^{-1}
 (Found* = 2.4832 g dl^{-1})

Sl. no. of mixture of oxidants	Amount of KIO_3 (g dl^{-1})		Standard deviation
	Actual	Found*	
1	3 478 0	3 391 7	$\pm 3.3 \times 10^{-2}$
2.	1 881 8	1 830 8	$\pm 7.5 \times 10^{-2}$
3.	0 871 5	0 876 7	$\pm 9.3 \times 10^{-4}$
4.	0 683 3	0.681 7	$\pm 3.7 \times 10^{-3}$
5.	0.542 7	0 541 4	$\pm 6.5 \times 10^{-4}$
6.	0 082 1	0 082 2	$\pm 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$

*Average of 6 determinations.

 TABLE 4—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF IO_3^- AND $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ FROM DIFFERENT MIXTURES (METHOD E)

Sl. no. of mixture of oxidations	Amount of KIO_3 (g dl^{-1})		Amount of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (g dl^{-1})	
	Actual	Found* (Standard deviation)	Actual	Found* (Standard deviation)
1.	3.616 0	3 608 8 ($\pm 3.2 \times 10^{-3}$)	5 384 9	5.378 9 ($\pm 5.9 \times 10^{-3}$)
2	1 524 1	1.531 8 ($\pm 7.29 \times 10^{-3}$)	2 284 6	2 280 9 ($\pm 2.1 \times 10^{-3}$)
3.	0.382 5	0.384 2 ($\pm 9.5 \times 10^{-4}$)	0 473 9	0 474 3 ($\pm 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$)
4.	0.356 3	0.351 7 ($\pm 7.6 \times 10^{-4}$)	0 473 9	0 474 3 ($\pm 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$)
5.	0.349 3	0.350 9 ($\pm 7.4 \times 10^{-4}$)	0 473 9	0 474 3 ($\pm 1.5 \times 10^{-3}$)
6.	0.156 6	0.156 6 ($\pm 2.1 \times 10^{-3}$)	0.314 7	0.318 5 ($\pm 5.3 \times 10^{-3}$)

*Mean of 6 determinations.

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